

MiniSQL regular queries

- `DROP TABLE` `TableName`
- `CREATE TABLE` `TableName` (`ColumnName` `DataType`[,`ColumnName` `DataType`...])
- `SELECT` `ColumnName`[,`ColumnName`...] `FROM` `Table` [`WHERE` `Condition`]
- `DELETE FROM` `TableName` `WHERE` `Condition`
- `INSERT INTO` `TableName` `VALUES` (`LiteralValue`[,`LiteralValue`, ...])
Note: There must be at least one value
- `UPDATE` `TableName` `SET` `ColumnName`=`LiteralValue`[,`ColumnName`=`LiteralValue`,...] `WHERE` `Condition`

DataType

`INT`

`DOUBLE`

`TEXT`

Condition

`ColumnName`<`LiteralValue`

`ColumnName`=`LiteralValue`

`ColumnName`>`LiteralValue`

LiteralValue

`'123'`, `'152'`, ... (INT)

`'3.42'`, `'-9.010'`, `'2'`, ... (DOUBLE)

`'Adolfo Sánchez'`, `'A'`,... (TEXT)

TableName, ColumnName

Only letters and numbers are accepted: `Table`, `Table1`, `MyTable`, ...

Notes:

- *The part of the specification inside brackets ([...]) is optional*
- *When the specification shows a whitespace, one or multiple whitespaces should be accepted*
- *When the specification shows no whitespace (i.e., between Column names), no whitespace should be accepted*

MiniSQL security queries

- `CREATE SECURITY PROFILE SecurityProfile`
- `DROP SECURITY PROFILE SecurityProfile`
- `GRANT PrivilegeType ON TableName TO SecurityProfile`
- `REVOKE PrivilegeType ON TableName TO SecurityProfile`
- `ADD USER (User, Password, SecurityProfile)`
- `DELETE USER User`

PrivilegeType

`DELETE`
`INSERT`
`SELECT`
`UPDATE`

SecurityProfile, User

Only letters are accepted: User, Admin, UserOne, UserTwo, ...

Notes:

- *A database can be created in two ways:*
 - *Creating an empty database from code (calling the constructor of Database). The username and password of the user are provided as arguments. This user is considered an administrator of the database and added to the profile Admin, that has full access to the database.*
 - *Loading a database from file (calling Database.Load). The database is loaded and it must be checked that the user's credentials exist in the database. Otherwise, the load will fail. In this case, the security profiles are loaded from the database.*
- *Security queries can only be done by users with the Admin profile.*
- *There is no specific privilege to create and drop tables. Only admins can do it.*